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P.O Box: 249 Buea Road, Kumba
Tel: (+237) 33354691 – Fax: (+237) 33354692
Email: editorinchief@httckumba.com
Website: <http://www.httckumba.com>

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Table of Contents

STUDY AND DESIGN OF A FOUR-PORTS HYBRID SOLAR/WIND DC-DC CONVERTER	1
Boukar Miri ¹ , Aloyem Kaze Claude ¹ , Ajamah Ferdinand ¹ , Tchouga Tchao Yannick ² , Ngouateu paigui ¹	
EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND MULTISCALE NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CRACKS IN VISCOELASTIC MATERIALS: APPLICATION TO BILINGA (NAUCLEADIDEERRICHI)	18
Mbelle Samuel Bisong* ^{1,2} , Tawe laynde ³ , Francois Njock Bayock ² , Valeriy V. Lepov ^{4,5} , Pierre Kisito Talla 6	
HARVESTING COMPOUNDS THE EFFECT OF WATER DEFICIT ON THE GROWTH AND YIELD OF WATER LEAF [TALINUM TRIANGULARE (JACQ.) WILLD.]	42
Dekoum VM Assaha* ¹ , Awasume Clovis Awasume ¹ , Pascal Tabi Tabot ¹ , Priscilla Mebong Mfombep ¹	
GEOLOCATION AND STUDY OF HOUSEHOLD WELL WATER IN RELATION TO CONTAMINANTS AS HEALTH MAPPING TOOL IN KUMBA, SOUTH WEST REGION, CAMEROON	55
BAHEL Benjamin ^{1,2} , NGWEM Bayiha Blaise ³ , Bate Esame Bate ¹ , NDIVE Martin Molua ¹ , Lissouck Daniel ⁴ , YAMB Emmanuel ³	
ANTHROPOMORPHISM AND GREEN ECONOMY: A STUDY OF JOHN NKEMNGONG NKENGASONG'S ANCESTRAL EARTH	72
Fomin Edward Efuat (Ph.D.)	
HUMAN EVOLUTION IN AFRICA AND GENETIC VARIATION: A GENETIC HISTORIAN'S INTERPRETATION	92
Forka Leypey Mathew Fomine	
THE PRAGMATICS OF CAMEROON ENGLISH	110
Menge Aaron Tabe	
FORMULATION OF A SNAIL-PROTEIN RICH MAIZE BASE WEANING FOOD (NutriPACK)	122
Samuel Metuge ^{1,2,3} , Asoba Gillian Nkeudem ^{1,2} , Tabe Frida Bawak ¹ , Ngede Laura Senge ¹ , Teh Rene Ning ² , Sumbele Irene Ule Ngole ²	
FORMULATION OF A YOGHURT LIKE PRODUCT FROM CORN MILK, SOY BEANS MILK, SKIMMED MILK ENRICHED WITH BANANA FLAVOUR	135
Mateing Cindry, Fidelis Sameh Ebong* ¹ , Asoba. Gilian Mofor ²	

CUSTOMER ATTRACTION AND RETENTION STRATEGIES IN VERY SMALL BUSINESSES: CASE OF BUTCHERIES IN LIMBE, CAMEROON152
Ndoko Alice Ekoi, Negou Ernest*², Nkenganyi Fonkem Marcellus³

CUSTOMER ATTRACTION AND RETENTION STRATEGIES IN VERY SMALL BUSINESSES: CASE OF BUTCHERIES IN LIMBE, CAMEROON

By

Ndoko Alice Ekoi, Negou Ernest*², Nkenganyi Fonkem Marcellus³

1. Senior Lecturer of Marketing, Department of Management Sciences, Higher Technical Teachers' Training College, University of Buea
2. Senior Lecturer, Department of Management Sciences, Higher Technical Teachers' Training College, Kumba, University of Buea
3. PLET, Lycee Technique Bilingue de Bonandoumbe, Douala

*Corresponding author: Negou Ernest, Tel: +237 675 096 933 / 693 118 250
E-mail: negou1@gmail.com

Abstract

The objective of this research is to assess how butchers who are typical examples of very small businesses attract and retain their customers in Limbe Municipality. To achieve this objective, the researcher used an exploratory research design on 10 meat sellers selected by convenience. A content-thematic analysis revealed that amongst the various strategies used by the meat sellers to attract and retain customers, positive attitude and behaviour, fairness and transparency, sales promotion and witchcraft are the most common. It was recommended that meat sellers should increase their interaction with customers, carry out more market research and improve their maintenance capacity.

Keywords: Customer Relationship Management, Very Small Businesses, customer retention and acquisition, Butchers, witchcraft.

1 Introduction

The relationship marketing concept is one of the marketing concepts that holds that consumers are the friends of the organisation; as such in satisfying their needs, the organisation must develop cordial and sustainable relationship with them. This concept dominated the world in the 80s and 90s. There are many definitions and interpretations of Customer Relationship Management (CRM). A general definition by Malik (2015), Rosalina and Malik (2019) and Khan et al. (2022) sees it as an enterprise approach to understanding and influencing customer behaviour through meaningful communications in order to improve customer acquisition, retention, loyalty and profitability. It concerns attracting, developing and retaining customer relationship (Chatterjee et al., 2020; Libai et al., 2020; Mehralian and Khazae, 2022; Migdadi, 2021; Nariya, 2023; Nuseir and Refae, 2022).

Without CRM, companies cannot meet customers' needs, neither can they value, acquire and retain customers. It is the strongest and the most efficient approach in maintaining and creating relationships with customers. It is not only pure business but also creates strong personal connection between people.

Unfortunately, very few organizations succeed in capturing real potentials of CRM especially in developing countries where demand is far less than supply in many domains. King and Burgess (2008) highlight that CRM change management, which includes both hard (technologies) and soft (people) aspects, is a defining factor between the success and the failure of CRM. The soft aspects of CRM involve influencing people's feelings, attitudes, mind-sets, and behaviours to achieve support for a CRM change (Desai and Sahu, 2008).

Studies by Kubkomawa et al. (2018, 2019) for example, revealed that beef production and marketing in Mubi, Adamawa State of Nigeria is predominated by sellers with limited western education, indicating limited change in the socio-cultural status of actors in the face of a rapidly changing marketing environment. This raises the question how do they attract and retain their customers without marketing knowledge and enough finances?

Also, Grönroos (1996) and Saungweme (2010) contend that inadequate financial resources coupled with little or no adoption of market research to uncover changing customer tastes and lack of technological innovations often constrain small business operators' ability to fully carry out effective CRM. Similarly, their lack of Management Information Systems (MISs) limits their ability to use them for competitive advantages.

Rababah et al. (2011) add that common causes of failures in CRM initiatives are the failing to re-engineer business processes, the business process not redefined prior to CRM implementation, and the difficulty in measuring the effectiveness of CRM deployment. As such, meat sellers (mainly very small business operators) have the tendency to indigenously practice CRM (without following sound scientific approaches) which may not be very effective in the background of growing competition amongst traders. This study aims at enlightening how very small businesses in their practice of CRM attract and retain their customers in developing countries in general and in Cameroon in particular.

2 Literature Review

Alipour and Hallaj Mohammadi (2011) carried out a research in a Truck making company of Tabriz in the form of case-study. Its purpose was to investigate the impact of CRM in order to gain the competitive advantage in industrialized manufactures of Truck. The study reveals the ability of the organizations to adjust themselves with the customer needs quickly as one of the attraction and retention strategy.

Soleymani et al. (2014) carried out a study to investigate the impact of Customer Relationship Marketing on Customer Satisfaction in the Banking Industry in KSA and Jordan. The study reveals the following Customer Relationship Management dimensions: trust, commitment, communication, empathy, social bonding and fulfilling promises and proves their great influence on customer satisfaction.

Azimi and Amiri (2018) studied the impact of satisfaction and trust on loyalty in mobile banking services among the faculties of Shiraz University. They confirmed that factors such as usability and customer services play a significant role in fulfilling the requirements of the consumers and yield trustworthiness to the great extent.

Gopalsamy and Gokulapadmanaban (2021) carried out a study on the effect of Implementation of CRM on Customer Loyalty in India. Results show that CRM has a positive influence on loyalty through customer knowledge management, customer satisfaction, and customer trust which are attraction and retention strategies.

The above literature constitutes the basis of this research. It reveals the following customer attraction and retention strategies: the ability of the organizations to adjust themselves with the customer needs quickly, trust, commitment, communication, empathy, social bonding, fulfilling promises, usability of the product, customer services, customer knowledge management and customer satisfaction. The sum of these findings points out the importance of this topic which aims at describing how butchereries which fall under Very Small Businesses in the classification of Small Businesses in Cameroon practice CRM in Limbe Municipality.

A number of theories or theoretical approaches have been used to explain the way in which companies use CRM to acquire, satisfy and retain customers. These theories are analysed in this section namely the IDIC model (Peppers and Rogers, 2004) which states that companies should take four actions (Identifying, Differentiating, Interacting, Customizing) in order to build closer one-to-one relationships with customers and the CRM Value Chain Model which traces the steps that businesses can follow when developing their CRM strategies (Buttle, 2004; Nariya, 2023).

3 Research Methodology

Different research on this topic has been carried out in developed nations, but in the African context, little is known on the practice of CRM by Very Small Businesses. It is to have a better understanding of the phenomenon that the exploratory research design is selected. A qualitative approach in this case is more indicated because it enables a deep interaction with key actors of the domain. Following this approach, 10 butchereries in the Limbe municipality are selected by convenience. This means that only butchereries within

the reach of the researcher are selected. The target population is made up of the main worker of the butchery who can be the owner or an apprentice. The number is limited to 10 because any additional interview was providing the same results, leading to theoretical saturation. The focus of this paper is on meat companies because they are typical examples of Very small businesses in Cameroon. The sampling size is of great concern for qualitative research. An acceptable sample size for multiple case study should have between 4 and 20 cases (Boddy, 2016; Hlady-Rispal, 2015; Hlady-Rispal et al., 2021; Lakens, 2022; McDermott, 2023; Rispal, 2002). The data is analysed using a thematic content-analysis technique. It refers to the process of categorizing verbal or behavioural data to classify, summarize and tabulate the data. Descriptive statistics is used to summarize the content analysis. Table 1 presents the cases.

Table 1: Presentation of cases

Socio-demographic variable	Meat seller 1	Meat seller 2	Meat seller 3	Meat seller 4	Meat seller 5	Meat seller 6	Meat seller 7	Meat seller 8	Meat seller 9	Meat seller 10
Sex	Male									
Age	33	39	50	41	38	25	50	31	45	50
Position	Apprentice	Manager	Manager	Manager	Manager	Apprentice	Manager	Manager	Manager	Manager
Experience	4 years	10 Years	22 Years	20 Years	13 Years	2 years	13 Years	10 years	10 years	10 years

Source: Field survey, 2023

Table 1 reveals that all butchers are male. Their age ranges from 25 to 50 years and their experiences from 2 to 22 years. 2 of them are apprentices while 8 others are owners and managers.

4 Results

4.1 Summary of the Customer Attraction Strategies Used by Meat Sellers in the Limbe Municipality

This section summarizes the strategies used by meat sellers to attract customers. This is done in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Summary of strategies used by all the sellers to attract customers

Strategies used	Corresponding meat sellers who selected that strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Sales promotion	1,2,5,7,8	5	11.11
Packaging	7	1	2.22

Fairness and transparency	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,9,10	9	20
Direct contact	1,4,6,8	4	8.88
Religious Belief	3,7,9,10	5	11.11
Positive attitude/ Behaviour towards customers	1,2,3,4,5,6,8,9,10	10	22.22
Physical Evidence	1,2,4,5,6,8,9	7	15.55
Positive word- of- mouth recommendation	2	1	2.22
Credit sales	2	1	2.22
Indifferent	3, 10	2	4.44
Total		45	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The above table represents a summary of the customer attraction strategies used by meat sellers in the Limbe Municipality. As it stands, most of the sellers attract their customers through positive attitude/behaviours, which gave a percentage of 22.22 and it is practiced by all the meat sellers. This was confirmed by seller 1 who said: 'I use good manner to approach our clients, we talk to them politely'. Seller 3 went further to add: 'I am always friendly and polite to everyone no matter your age. I greet all my customers who come to buy and ask how they are ferrying and always wear a smile''

This was followed by fairness and transparency with 20%. Through this strategy, the meat sellers attract customers by using the right measuring scale and cutting good slices of meat as confirmed by seller 7: 'I use the right measuring scale and cut my meat in the recommended slices'. Amongst the strategies, 5 meat sellers dwell their belief on religion where they base their trust on God and also on witchcraft to bring customers and protect that business which gave an 11.11% out of the 100% as attested by seller 9: 'I protect my business place through the African way'. The least strategies used was positive word-of-mouth recommendation, credit sales and packaging as an attraction strategy which gave a 2.22% each.

4.2 Summary of Retention Strategies Used by Meat Sellers in the Limbe Municipality

This section summarizes the strategies used by meat sellers to retain customers.

Table 3: Summary of retention strategies used by sellers

Strategies used	Meat Sellers Who choose This Option	Frequency	Percentage
Home Delivery	1,2,5,8,10	5	12.19
Fairness and Transparency	2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10	9	21.95
Religious Belief	3,7,10	4	9.75
Witchcraft practices	9	1	2.43
Positive attitude/ Behaviour towards customers	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10	10	24.39
Regular communication	1,2,4,5,7,8,9	7	17.07
Sales Promotion	1,2,5,7,8	5	12.19

Total		41	100
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Source: Field Survey, 2023

With regards to the customer retention strategies (objective two), results on the table above reveal that there are many similarities between the customer attraction and retention strategies used by meat sellers in Limbe. Overlapping customer attraction and retention strategies in this study include: positive behaviour / attitudes to guests, fairness, and sales promotion. However, results on Table 3 indicates that home delivery service and regular communication were distinct retention strategies different from attraction strategies.

Based on the above table, most of the meat sellers used positive attitude and behaviour, fairness and transparency as a retention strategy with percentages of 24.39% and 21.95% respectively to retain their customers. This was confirmed by seller 4: 'Everyone likes to be welcome or treated fairly, so I use this strategy by talking politely to everyone who comes to me while calling them by their names'. Seller 6 added: 'I retain my customers by approaching them in a friendly manner, communicating with them through the phone or face to face to create a strong relationship. 'This makes the customers to become loyal since the communication helps me to know their exact needs, complaints and also makes adjustments where and when necessary. Also I sell to my customers using the right measuring scales and cutting the recommended sizes of meat because it is just but natural that people will always come back where they do not feel cheated'.

The least strategy used by the meat sellers in the Limbe municipality was the witchcraft practices with a 2.43%, followed by the religious believes. Meat seller 9 supported this view by affirming: 'I dwell my trust on witchcraft to protect my business since I have been attacked many times by my competitors spiritually. I use medicine to protect myself and my business.' According to him, the use of medicine is mostly to retain his customers. This makes them to always buy from him. Protection medicine following their view has no influence on the quality of the product, but increases customers' interest. This is a very subjective practice because it has not yet been verified empirically.

5 Conclusion

Besides other specific objectives, the following study investigates the practice of CRM by meat sellers in the Limbe municipality. To achieve the research objectives, the population of the study was made up of meat sellers in the Limbe municipality. The convenience non-probability sampling technique was used to select 10 butchers. Data for this study was collected through semi-structured interview. The instrument used to collect data is the interview guide.

The researcher summarizes the content-thematic analysis in descriptive statistics tables. The result indicated that the meat sellers in the various markets in the Limbe municipality are male, with a majority of them above the ages of 30 years.

To better understand the attraction strategies used by the meat seller, a content-thematic analysis revealed that amongst the various strategies suggested by the meat sellers,

positive attitude and behaviour was the most used amongst the strategies by the meat sellers to attract customers which gave a 22.22%, followed by fairness and transparency which have a 20%. This was followed by physical evidence with a 15.55%. Sales promotion and religious beliefs were considered by the meat sellers as another customer attraction strategy with a 11.11% from their response, direct contact, indifference, credit sales, positive word-of-mouth and packaging was the least strategy used by the meat sellers to attract their customers with a total of 8.88%, 4.44%, 2.22%, 2.22% and 2.22% respectively

With regards to the customer retention strategies which was the second objective of the study, the results revealed that there were similarities between the customer attraction and retention strategies used by meat sellers in Limbe like positive behaviour /attitudes to guests with a 24.39%, fairness and transparency follows with a 21.95%, and sales promotion with a 12.19. However, results indicates that regular communication is necessary for customer retention which gave a 17.07%. Home delivery service scores 12.19% just like the sales promotion strategy, followed by religious beliefs and the least strategy that was adapted by most of the meat sellers was witchcraft practices.

Considering the fact that meat is a necessity and that people eat it every day, giving its nutritional benefits to the human body, the following recommendations are made to improve on the practices of meat sellers in the Limbe municipality:

The association of meat seller should ensure that the prices for meat and its recommended slices cut be respected by all the meat sellers so as to avoid cheating on customers which they are trying to serve.

Although customers can be troublesome at times, the meat sellers should try to adopt a calm and understanding spirit to deal with customers of all categories so as to create and maintain a good relationship with them.

Also, meat sellers should involve themselves into home delivery services since most people are very busy and will not have time to come to the market to buy.

Again, meat sellers should increase their interaction with customers to know their exact needs, likes, preferences and complaints so as to better serve them. This can be done through the use of technologies like phones to reach most of their customers

As much as possible, meat sellers should do market research in order to understand the preferences, needs and expectation of customers from them.

Finally, meat sellers should build a big cold house to store their left-over meat.

This research does not go without implications among which the theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically the research implies that very small businesses just like large businesses effectively practice CRM to remain competitive in their domain. The techniques used are almost the same as those used by large businesses but to a lesser extent and to a less systematic manner.

Practically this research implies that despite their low level of education and the limited budget, meat sellers practice customer relationship to increase their sales.

For further studies, it is suggested that the study to be extended to other Very small businesses nationwide. It is also suggested that more studies be carried out on the use of witchcraft as marketing attraction and retention techniques.

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